

Invesalius and navigated TMS using Polhemus Patriot

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Abstract

This document aims to provide guidance on the installation and use of the InVesalius Neuronavigator in conjunction with the Polhemus Patriot three-dimensional tracking system. This setup offers the advantage of being more cost-effective than stereoscopic tracking camera systems. Detailed installation and operation instructions are provided for both the hardware and software components, including procedures for defining reference points on the medical image, the patient's head, and the stimulation coil. Additional instructions are included for initiating neuronavigation and identifying key scalp targets for transcranial stimulation. Previous studies on system characterization and measurement validation are referenced to situate this work within the existing literature.

Keywords

Medical image / Image processing / Computational neuronavigation

Specifications table

Hardware name	Polhemus Patriot (https://polhemus.com/)
Software name	InVesalius Neuronavigator (https://github.com/invesalius/invesalius3)
Subject area	Neuroscience
Hardware type	Field measurements and sensors

1. Introduction

This document aims to guide the installation and use of the Invesalius Neuronavigator with the three-dimensional tracker Polhemus Patriot. The Polhemus Patriot is a wireless magnetic tracking system that offers 6 degrees of freedom and tracking for two objects simultaneously. The sensors are updated at a rate of 60 Hz, which provides a smooth and constant update of the coil (sensor 1) relative to the patient's head (sensor 2). This system has the advantage of being more cost-effective than other high-end alternatives. However, navigation should be performed in an environment free of metal structures near the equipment, which is somewhat restrictive in laboratory and healthcare settings. After installation and definition of reference points, it is possible to perform neuronavigation and define important targets on the scalp.

The solution for running Polhemus on the Invesalius Neuronavigator was created for Visual Studio 2015, having been compiled and executed, resulting in a Python file and a .pyd file.

These files are the Python library that executes the spatial tracker functions. The libraries were named polhemus, polhemusFT for Polhemus Patriot, and Polhemus Fastrak (Matsuda, 2018).

This tutorial is organized into two parts. The first part covers the installation of the Invesalius modules and the Polhemus PiMgr 2.7.0 software, which connects to the Polhemus Patriot system and performs basic operation and location tests. The second part explains the installation and use of Polhemus with the Invesalius Neuronavigator. To access the manufacturer's manual, please refer to the manufacturer's [website](#). For more details on the operation of the complete InVesalius Neuronavigator system, please refer to the document at the following address ([link](#)). The important links involved in this tutorial are the following: [invesalius3-master](#), [miniconda3](#), [PiMgrSetup](#), [SWD-install](#), and [PATRIOT Manual](#). Please get in touch with the Polhemus manufacturer for further information on Patriot™ Software and SDK.

2. Polhemus Patriot installation instructions

First, connect the Polhemus Patriot power adapter to a 110 Volt outlet and connect the 12V plug to the input on the back panel of the device. Connect the plugs for sensor 1 (stylus), sensor 2 (cube), and power supply (antenna) to the front panel. After everything is connected, turn the device on using the "on/off" switch and wait about 10 seconds until the front LED turns green.

CAUTION: Do not disconnect or connect the antenna while the PATRIOT is powered on. Ensure that the power cable is physically separated from the sensor cables.

Run the PI Tracker Management GUI program (when available¹) by double-clicking the icon created on the desktop. To check which serial port is available and can be used, go to Windows Device Manager (Windows key + X then "M" > System Tools > Device Manager) and check the serial port in the sub-list (Ports (COM & LPT)). In this case, the available port is COM1

Figure 1. Device Manager dialog to check the serial port in the sub-list (Ports: COM & LPT).

¹ If this software is somehow not available, just check which serial port is being used, define the communication parameters as in Figure 2 and go straight to step 3 below in this tutorial.

Figure 2. Shortcut for running the PI Tracker Management GUI program.

In the PI Tracker Management GUI (when available), click the Device menu > Tracker Configuration (Ctrl-Z), select the Connection tab, Connection type: RS-232. Choose the COM1 port used on the computer and baud rate of 115,200, parity None. You can also define these parameters in the Device Manager dialog, by right clicking on the COM1 port > Properties > Tab Port Configuration.

Figure 3. Dialog to define connection type and speed.

To establish the connection, click the Toggle Connection icon (Alt-X), which should display a connected message at the bottom of the window.

Figure 4. Main screen of the PI Tracker Manager, indicating the button (shortcut: Alt-X) to establish the connection between the computer and the Polhemus Patriot console.

Click Yes in the dialog box asking “Sync Current Configuration from Device”. At this point, only two colored airplanes will appear on the screen, one for the stylus and the other for sensor 2.

Immediately after connecting, verify that the text “Tracker connected via serial port” appears in the lower bar of the screen. Additionally, the program should display the Tracker name just below the menus, along with the 3D coordinates of each sensor. The colored planes should follow the movement of the sensors in the three-dimensional space around the antenna. Remember to use only the positive quadrant of the antenna, as shown in the diagram below (Figure 9).

Figure 5. Main screen of the PI Tracker Manager, indicating that the connection was established. By clicking on the green arrow, the user can obtain the numerical values of the three-dimensional coordinates.

To test navigation stability, check whether the aircraft exhibits smooth and constant movement as the stylus and sensor are moved in space. If there is vibration, jumps, erratic or noisy movement, ensure that there are no metal objects near the antenna or receivers (stylus or sensor 2). Verify whether the line of sight between the antenna and sensors is free of obstacles. Additionally, you can click the green arrow (Toggle Continuous Mode - Alt-X) to obtain the numerical values of the three-dimensional coordinates.

3. Polhemus Patriot in InVesalius instructions

Install the miniconda and check and copy the path to the installation directory (something like "C:\Users\YourUserName\miniconda"). After that, install the program [SWD-25602-13-3.0.3-PatUSBDrvPkgInstall.exe](#). Copy the invesalius3 folder to a directory on your computer. The Invesalius3 folder is located inside the invesalius3-master folder.

Open the Miniconda command line prompt and enter the conda terminal and navigate using the cd (change directory) command to the invesalius3 folder. There you can run the command: “conda env create -f environment.yml --name invesalius”. This installs and defines a new virtual environment.

After installation, copy the files from the [repository](#) and paste them inside the `invesalius3\invesalius_cy` folder. Do that by choosing the folder inside the zip files with the name according to your installed Python version (`python-3.11`). Then, run the command: `conda activate invesalius` and run the command: `python app.py`

Physically connect the Polhemus Patriot, remembering to keep all metal objects away from the equipment before and during navigation. The stylus should be connected to the Sensor 1 input, the head marker to Sensor 2, and the antenna to the Source input. Lastly, enable navigation in Invesalius using the Preferences menu.

Figure 6. Use the Preferences menu to Enable navigation in Invesalius

In the Tracker tab, select the Polhemus Patriot tracker type.

Figure 7. In the Preferences dialog, open the tab Tracker to select the Polhemus Patriot tracker.

Define the fiducials in the 3D image (right-click on the 3D volume and then click on the name of the fiducial (Left Tragus, Nasion, Right Tragus).

Figure 8. Location of left tragus (LEI) and right tragus (REI) and Nasion (NAS) points on the reconstructed volume of the sample CT inside Invesalius.

The transmitting antenna should be positioned on the right posterior region (behind and to the right) of the subject, with the antenna origin and cable at the point furthest from the center of the head (see top view diagram in Figure 9 below). In this way, the navigation will be performed in the positive quadrant of the antenna, as indicated on the upper surface of the transmitting antenna. Sensor 2 (small cube) can be fixed to the right side of the patient's head with micropore tape or adhesive bandage. Sensor 1 (stylus) should be fixed to the upper surface of the coil pointing forward.

Figure 9. Bird's eye view of the setup, considering the location of the Polhemus emitter in relation to the patient's head. Note the orientation of the emitter. Emitter cable enters the box along the x axis. The Y axis must be pointing forward. Emitter must be positioned on the posterior right quadrant of the patient's head.

Collect the fiducial points on the head using the Polhemus stylus after clicking on the Patient tab, then Start Patient Registration. Place the tip of sensor 1 on the left ear tragus and click the Left Ear button, which will then turn green. Locate the stylus on the other points on the head (Nasion and Right Ear), clicking the respective button. Try to keep the sensor perpendicular to the surface of the head when collecting the points. By clicking the Next button, you can check the fiducial error (FRE), which should be below 5. Refine the co-registration if necessary.

Figure 10. Patient registration tab, with the "Start patient registration" option already clicked, Left ear already recorded and Nasion location ready to be acquired.

In the TMS coil tab, click Preferences, then the "New" button to collect the coil reference points. Click "Yes" to use the default Invesalius object.

Figure 11. Tab TMS Coil to register the coil reference points by clicking Preferences. You can register the coil (by clicking New) or load an existing registration file (by clicking Load).

The coil should be positioned next to the patient, between the patient and the antenna, as shown in Figure 9. Points to the left and right of the coil should coincide with the same sides of the patient. Then, leave the coil static, horizontally positioned and oriented forward in the direction the patient is looking, as shown above.

Collect the points located to the left, right, and center of the coil using the Polhemus stylus, using the lower surface of the coil as a reference.

Figure 12. The buttons turn green after all points are registered.

Attach the stylus to the coil before clicking the “Fixed” button. Click Done and OK. Click "Proceed to neuronavigation", then click on "Start Neuronavigation" and verify that the location in the real world matches the location navigated in 3D.

Figure 13. Testing the location of the coil in relation to the head, to confirm the corregistration was correctly set up.

When you reach a desired point, for instance on the top of the motor cortex, click "Create marker". Then, right-click on the bookmark list. On the newly created bookmark, click "Set as target".

Figure 14. The newly created marker appears at the end of the marker list, right after the fiducial markers. When setting markers with navigation enabled, they are created in the "Coil target" category. Clicking "Set as target" defines the marker as the target. You can rename the marker by clicking the Change label.

Click on "Start navigation". Move the coil closer to the target by orienting your movement using the arrows around the coil icons on the right side of the screen (rotation in y, rotation in z, rotation in x). Translations can be adjusted by checking the Distance value in the lower left corner of the 3D view.

Figure 15. Bird's eye view in the 3D viewport of the navigation screen. Colored coils in green indicate that either roll, pitch and yaw are already correctly accomplished.

To make longer stimulation sessions, stabilize the TMS coil using an adjustable coil holder or stand designed for medical use. The magnetic pulses generated by the stimulator may inject transient noise into the Polhemus Tracker. Navigation quality may be poor for a short period of time. The operator should decide whether it is necessary to remove the stylus during stimulation. If you need to restart Invesalius, turn *Polhemus Patriot* off and on again to establish a new connection.

4. Validation and characterization

The co-registration method using the Polhemus Patriot was previously characterized and evaluated to assess performance and reliability (Souza *et al.*, 2018). Metrics and criteria were defined to quantify accuracy, including positional error between reference and registered data. Tests under controlled conditions (phantoms or standard objects) were performed to measure how well the method aligns instruments or images. Sources of error like tracking inaccuracies, calibration, and misalignment were considered to identify how they affect final registration accuracy. Reproducibility tests by repeating the co-registration procedure multiple times were carried out and variation was evaluated across runs.

CRedit author statement

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